

ZERO
WASTE

THINK
GREEN

NO
PLASTIC

ECO
FRIENDLY

FULL
RECO4US

Bilig
DÜĞÜŞEL AKADEMİ
UPCYCLING ACADEMY

innobrane

ISTANBUL2023

**International Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies
Towards Zero Waste (FULLRECO4US) Conference**

13 – 15 September 2023

Istanbul, Turkey

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International Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies Towards Zero Waste (FULLRECO4US) Conference
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Preface

On behalf of the organizing committee, I would like to welcome all participants and speakers to the International Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies Towards Zero Waste (FULLRECO4US) Conference in Istanbul/Turkiye. This conference is the first international conference under Cost Action 20133: Cross Border Transfer and Development of Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies Towards Zero Waste (FULLRECO4US) and I hope it will be the starting point for a series of FULLRECO4US conferences. It is my pleasure to thank COST Action 20133 (funded by the European Union) for their financial support.

FULLRECO4US Istanbul 2023 conference provides a unique opportunity for professionals from around the world to learn, share and present the latest knowledge and insights on circular economy, zero waste, resource recovery strategies, energy resources and sustainable food systems. The conference is a networking platform with the world's leading experts in resource recovery strategies and related fields. It is an important event for assessing the key challenges in promoting a sustainable zero waste bringing together an international community of leading academics, researchers, engineers and industry professionals to exchange and share their ideas and experiences.

This conference was organized in Istanbul by Innobrane Research Group led by Derya Y. Koseoglu-Imer and Bilig Upcycling Academy. The local organizing team, which are members of Innobrane Research Group, consists of Derya Y. Koseoglu-Imer (conference chair), Sama Al-Mutwalli (conference secretariat), Tugba Sapmaz-Wikstrom (conference secretariat), Mustafa Taher (conference secretariat), Elifnur Gezmis Yavuz, Esra Buyukada Kesici, Feyza Nur Buyuknalçaci, Sezer Gençturk, Yasin Sahin, Duygu Tozaraydin, Cagri Kaan Kilic. There was also an international organizing committee composed of 10 members from 9 different countries: Mohammad Taherzadeh (SE), Philippe Corvini (CH), Pieter Billen (BE), Olga Nunes (PT), Jorge Marchetti (NO), Patrik Lennartsson (SE), Timo Kikas (EE), Belen Garcia (ES), Gjore Nakov (BG), Derya Y. Koseoglu-Imer (TR). The scientific committee of the conference included 120 reviewers from 36 countries. We had 2 plenary speakers, 7 keynote speakers, 7 stakeholders, 57 oral presentations, and 51 poster presentations and more than 200 participants from 35 countries. The conference showed a good balance in terms of gender equality: 57% of the participants were women and 43% were men.

It is my pleasure to thank Prof. Mohammad J. Taherzadeh (COST Action Chair) and all members of the core group and management committee of COST Action-20133, members of local organizing team, all participants, stakeholders, Kolektif House, Bilig Academy and Crowlink who contributed to success of this conference.

Istanbul is truly a crossroads of ideas and cultures between Europe and Asia. I hope that all participants had good memories of the FULLRECO4US Istanbul Conference.

See you again in Istanbul, Sincerely

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Derya Y. Koseoglu-Imer (Conference Chair)

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Hydrochar production from waste lignocellulosic biomass with recirculation of process water

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Abstract

The utilization of biowaste and its transformation into alternative sources of energy is a trend, which could help reduction of carbon emissions and support increasing demand for energy, as well as to solve the growing environmental problems related to solid waste. One of the alternative sources of energy is hydrochar (HC) which is produced using hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) of various wet biomass wastes. During the HTC process, process water in subcritical state is used as a reaction medium to convert biomass into HC. Process water from HTC represents a liquid by-product, rich in organic (polyphenols, flavonoids, dietary fibers, etc.) and inorganic compounds that can have negative impacts on the environment if the water is not properly managed. One of the ways to avoid contamination by releasing process water into the environment, as well as the application of expensive treatments for its purification, is to repeatedly use it in HTC process (i.e. recirculation). The reuse of process water in HTC has been gaining interest due to its potential contribution to the circular economy (closing the water loop), environmental protection, and health. In this paper, the characteristics of the HCs obtained with the recirculation of process water in four consecutive cycles are examined. The HTC process was carried out in a commercial stainless-steel reactor at 300 °C, a pressure of 20 bar (autogenous pressure), while a solid/liquid ratio was 1:15. Waste wood biomass was used as feedstock. The yield of HC in the first run was 40%, while the carbon content was amounted to 79 wt.%. Furthermore, the obtained HC was characterized with relatively high higher heating value (HHV) of 2561 kJ/100 g. In the case of the HTC process with process water recirculation, an increase in the HC yield was recorded for all the runs (up to 10%), while the carbon content remained at the approximately same value. During the process with recirculation, HHV value increased with increasing the number of recirculation cycles (up to 3095 kJ/100 g in the fourth cycle), which indicates that organic matter from the liquid phase has been incorporated into the HC structure contributing to its yield, as well as its quality as an alternative source of energy.

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